

DEBONDING PROPAGATION RATE IN SINGLE NITI SHAPE MEMORY FIBRE COMPOSITE

Yousef Payandeh¹, Fodil Meraghni¹, Etienne Patoor¹, André Eberhardt²

Laboratoire de Physique et Mécanique des Matériaux (LPMM-UMR CNRS 7554)

1- ENSAM, 4 rue Augustin Fresnel, 57078, Metz, France

2- ENIM, Ile du Saulcy, 57045, Metz, France

(Tel.: +33 387 37 54 30. Email address: Yousef.payandeh@metz.ensam.fr)

Abstract

The debonding propagation in single NiTi shape memory fibre epoxy matrix composite was investigated using the pull-out test. Three different heat treatment cycles have been performed in order to obtain fibres with different transformational characteristics. The single fibre composite samples have been prepared with the use of an epoxy -amine mixture as the matrix material. The composite was then cured, post-cured and cooled to room temperature. The in-situ observations of the interfacial debonding and sliding behaviour during the pull-out test were carried out using a digital camera which has been located in back of a polariscope. From in-situ observation, the debonding begins from fibre entry point and proceeds to the embedded end. It is observed that when there is no phase transformation the debonding propagates rapidly whilst it is slow when there is fibre phase transformation or martensitic reorientation. In the case where the debonding begins at the applied stress less than the transformational stress, the debonding rate decreases as soon as the fibre reaches the phase transformation. The debonding rate has been calculated for the different samples. It is found that the debonding rate depends on the displacement rate as well as the length change during phase transformation.

Key words: NiTi fibre composite; Debonding rate; Interfacial shear strength; Pull-out test.

1. Introduction

Shape Memory Alloys (SMAs) are metallic alloys that can undergo martensitic phase transformations as a result of applied thermomechanical loads and are capable of recovering permanent strains when heated above a certain temperature. At high temperatures the crystal lattice is in a high symmetry, parent austenitic phase. The key characteristic of all SMAs is the occurrence of a martensitic phase transformation between the austenitic phase and the different variants of the low temperature, low symmetry martensitic phase. The martensitic transformation is a shear-dominant diffusionless solid-state phase transformation occurring by nucleation and growth of the martensitic phase from the parent austenitic phase [1].

In near equiatomic Ti-Ni alloys, the shape memory effect and superelasticity occur in association with the thermoelastic martensitic transformation from the parent phase (β) with a B2 structure to the phase with a monoclinic B19' structure, or more often in association with the two-step transformation from the β to a trigonal phase (so called R-phase) and then to the B19' phase [2].

In order to guaranty adequate stiffness and ultimate strength of structural elements, together with high durability and long-term performance, SMAs are sometime embedded into a plastic or metallic matrix. [3] Nevertheless, some fibre characteristics change during phase transformation that can affect the interfacial properties. Therefore, prior to implementing these composites into the real structures, it needs to work on the fibre phase transformation and interfacial characteristics of these kinds of composite

It is well recognized that the mechanical behaviour of many composite materials depends largely on the properties of the fibre/matrix interface [4-7]. One of the fundamental problems in the field of fibre-polymer composites deals with the control of the degree of adhesion between the usually more rigid fibre and the relatively ductile polymer matrix [8]. In fact, the interfacial debonding between fibre and matrix is the most important factor which leads to the failure of composite materials [9, 10]. It is obvious that when shear stress between constituents increases upon the interfacial shear strength, interfacial debonding will start immediately. It is generally agreed that the higher the critical debonding stress, the stronger the composite material will be [9]. In fact, when the composites are loaded, stress transfer would take place across the fibre/matrix interface. The mechanical properties of the composites depend critically upon the efficiency of the stress transfer during fibre pull-out [4]. A composite system with large interfacial shear strength, τ_i , (excellent fibre-matrix bonding) has high strength due to effective stress transfer from the matrix to the fibres [6].

The fibre pull-out test has been well accepted as one of the most important test methods developed as a means of investigating the interfacial adhesion quality and interfacial properties between fibres and matrix and the elastic stress transfer in the fibre pull-out problem [4-6, 8, 11-16].

In the present work, the debonding propagation in single fibre composite was investigated. The shape memory NiTi fibre with different phase transformation parameters have been employed in order to characterize the bonding characteristics.

2. Experimental procedure

The composite material studied in this work is a near equiatomic NiTi shape memory fibre epoxy matrix composite. The fibre of 1 mm diameter in the work hardened condition was supplied by the Nimesis Company. Several heat treatment cycles have been chosen in order to have the shape memory fibre with different transformation characteristics. The transformation temperatures were identified, using the DSC technique (table 1). The oxide layer was then removed from the fibre surface, and then the fibre was cleaned and dried. The NiTi wires show the Austenite (B2) \rightarrow R-phase \rightarrow Martensite (B19') transformation sequence on cooling and the B19' \rightarrow B2 on heating.

An epoxy -amine mixture was cast into a preheated metallic mould in which a single NiTi fibre was located in the centre of each hole. The composite was then cured at 140 °C for 1 h, post-cured for 2-5 h at 165 °C and cooled to room temperature.

The composite specimen is a cylinder with diameter and length of 15 and 50 mm, respectively. The embedded fibre length, L , is 50 mm which corresponded to a fibre aspect ratio of $L/2a \approx 50$. The nominal fibre volume fraction equals to 0.44 %.

The composite specimen was put under a metallic piece, which had a 3 mm diameter hole at the centre; this diameter is 3 times larger than the fibre diameter. The centre of the fibre was placed at the centre of the hole in order to allow the fibre to be pulled out freely from the specimen. The pull-out test was conducted in air at room temperature (298 K) by fixing the metallic piece and applying a tensile load to the free end of the fibre at a constant displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. The experimental set-up was shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1. The transformation temperatures ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for different heat treatments.

Alloy	Heat treatment	M_f	M_s	R_f	R_s	A_s	A_f
M- 550	550 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 30 min	20	34	34	40	58	71
M- 450	450 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 60 min	-21	2	44	51	50	65
M- 400	400 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 60 min	≈ -45	≈ -25	49	60	49	65

Fig.1–Experimental set-up (a) side section (b) up view

The in-situ observations of the interface debonding and sliding behaviour during the pull-out test were carried out using a digital camera which has been located in back of polariscope. Several photos have been taken during the experiment. The results are shown in the Fig. 2.

3. Results and discussion

The mechanical behaviour of the fibre is shown in Fig. 3 a - c. The M-550 fibres are martensitic which was formed in self-accommodating manner. In the M-400 and M-450 fibres, the stable phase at room temperature is R-phase. Thus, by applying the external stress, the martensitic reorientation occurs in M-550 whilst in M-450 and M-400, at first the reorientation of the R-phase occurs and then the martensitic transformation takes place. The stress at which the martensite reorients in the M-550 fibres is about 100 MPa ($F \approx 80$ N) at room temperature. In the case of M-450 fibres the martensitic transformation occurs under a stress about 140 MPa ($F \approx 110$ N). The M-400 fibres transform to martensite under a stress about 250 MPa ($F \approx 200$ N) at the same temperature.

When the fibres are embedded in the matrix the free part of the fibres behaves same as above; but the embedded part can not behave freely. By applying a load on free end of the fibre, the Maximum Interfacial Shear Stress, MISS, will be at the fibre's entry point (where the fibre enters to the matrix).

The MISS increases with increasing the normal applied stress. When the MISS reaches a value denoted by, τ_i (interfacial shear strength), it remains constant and no longer increases with applied stress. Moreover, the debonding starts as soon as the MISS reaches τ_i , and propagates while the load is applied. With propagation of debonding, the MISS will be at the debonded/ undebonded transition zone. In the other word, the position of maximum shear stress varies with propagation of the debonding process [17].

Fig. 2- Debonding propagation along the fibre embedded length during the test. M-550 NiTi fibre. The first image (left hand side) was taken before test and the last one was taken just after completed debonding. The arrows show the position of debonding.

Fig. 3- Stress -Strain diagram for a) M-550, b) M-450 and c) M-400 fibres

According to in-situ observation (Fig. 2), the debonding starts from the fibre entry point and proceeds to the embedded end along the interface until the entire fibre is debonded. This process occurs slowly and when the bonded length reaches a critical embedded length the debonding phenomenon continues so rapidly. The fibre is then pulled out of the resin matrix by a frictional pull-out process. Fig. 4 shows the debonding rate versus time for the specimens with M-550 fibres. From this figure, apart from the last step, the debonding rate varies between 8.3 and 8.9 mm/min. In the last part the debonding propagate with the rate of 14.1 mm/min. The mean value is equal to 9.2 mm/ min.

The specimens with M-400 fibres are debonded more rapidly in comparison with the M-550 and M-450 fibres. In contrary, the debonding stress, at which the debonding process begins, in this case, is less than that for the samples with M-550 and M-450 fibre. In the other word, the interfacial failure, for the M-400, starts in low values of stress, proceeds faster in comparison with the M-550 and M-450 fibres. In the M-400 specimens, the debonding stresses are always less than the transformational stresses (Fig. 5) whilst these are greater than transformational stress in the M-550 and M-450 samples (Fig. 6). In the other words, in the cases of M-450 and M-550, the debonding takes place after transformation of the

free part of the fibre and in the M-400 specimens the debonding begins before transformation. In some specimens with M-400 fibre the phase transformation occurs before that the entire interface is debonded (Fig. 5 b). In such cases, the debonding rate decreases as soon as the transformation begins.

Fig. 4- Debonding rate for a specimen with M-550 fibre

Fig. 5- Force - Displacement diagram for the specimens with M-400 fibre (a) without and (b) with transformation

Fig. 6- Force - Displacement diagram for the specimens with (a) M-550 and (b) M450 fibre

Therefore, it can be claimed that the length changes during martensitic reorientation in M-550 or martensitic transformation in M-450 or sometimes in M-400 is the sole reason of decreasing in debonding rate. In the specimens with M-400, because there is no phase transformation, the interface debonds fast.

4. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge Nimesis Company, A. Nachit and M. Wary for their useful help and Lonza group for supplying of Lonzacure Detda 80.

Reference

1. Olson, G. B., Cohen, M. Stress assisted isothermal martensitic transformation: Application to TRIP steels. *Metall. Trans.* 1982. A 13A, 1907–1914.
2. Saburi T. Ti—Ni shape memory alloys, chapter 3. shape memory materials. Edited by Otsuka K., Wayman CM.. Cambridge University Press; 1999.
3. S. Marfia. Micro–macro analysis of shape memory alloy composites. *International Journal of Solids and Structures* 2005; 42: 3677–3699.
4. Fu SY, Yue CY, Hu X, Mai YW. Analyses of the micromechanics of stress transfer in single- and multi-fibre pull-out tests. *Composites Science and Technology* 2000; 60: 569-579.
5. Gao YC, Zhou LM. Energy release rate for interface debonding with prestress and friction. *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics* 1999; 32: 203-207.
6. Yue CY, Looi HC, Quek MY. Assessment of fibre-matrix adhesion and interfacial properties using the pull-out test. *Int J Adhesion and Adhesives* 1995; 15: 73 -80.
7. Yallee R B, Young R J. Evaluation of interface fracture energy for single-fibre composites. *Composites Science and Technology* 1998; 58: 1907 -1916.
8. Zhou XF, Nairn JA, Wagner HD. Fibre–matrix adhesion from the single-fibre composite test: nucleation of interfacial debonding. *Composites Part A* 1999; 30:1387–1400.
9. Poon CK, Lau KT, Zhou LM. Design of pull-out stresses for prestrained SMA wire/polymer hybrid composites. *Composites Part B: Engineering* 2005; 36 (1): 25-31.
10. Guo S, Honda K, Kagawa Y. Interface debonding from bottom face and frictional transition during push-out testing of a tungsten fibre-epoxy matrix composite. *Composites Science and Technology* 2005; 65: 1808–1814.
11. Wang X, Hu G. Stress transfer for a SMA fibre pulled out from an elastic matrix and related bridging effect. *Composites Part A* 2005; 36:1142–1151.
12. Vazquez-Rodriguez JM, Herrera-Franco PJ, Gonzalez-Chi PI. Analysis of the interface between a thermoplastic fibre and a thermosetting matrix using photoelasticity. *Composites Part A* 2007; 38: 819-827.
13. Quek MY. Stress transfer at a partially bonded fibre/matrix interface. *Int J of Adhesion & Adhesives* 2002; 22: 303–310.
14. Poon CK, Zhou LM, Yam LH. Size effect on the optimum actuation condition for SMA-composites. *Composite Structures* 2004; 66(1-4): 503-511.
15. Bannister D J, Andrews M C, Cervenka A J, Young R J. Analysis of the single-fibre pull-out test by means of Raman spectroscopy. Part II: Micromechanics of deformation for an aramid-epoxy system. *Composites Science and Technology* 1995; 53: 411-421.
16. Beckert W, Lauke B. Critical discussion of the single-fibre pull-out test: does it measure adhesion. *composites science and technology* 1997; 57: 1689-1706.
17. Payandeh Y, Meraghni F, Patoor E, Eberhardt A. Interfacial Shear Strength and Debonding in a NiTi Shape Memory Fibre-Epoxy Matrix Composite. Submitted.